

ADVANCES IN BIOMASS GASIFICATION FOR THE PRODUCTION OF BIOHEAT, BIOELECTRICITY AND BIOFUELS

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ABSTRACT: Current barriers to increase the use of bioenergy for different applications are first discussed. Then, recent advances are presented on gasification-based technologies to overcome these barriers that have been reached at TU Graz together with several partners. Gasification-based fuel bed concepts integrated in biomass combustion can significantly reduce emissions for bioheat production. Advances are presented for modern biomass boilers, significantly reducing nitrogen oxides and particle matter emissions as well as increasing the feedstock flexibility; and micro-gasifiers for traditional biomass utilization, significantly reducing the emissions of unburnt products. Gasification-based processes have as well the possibility to score high electrical efficiencies and to synthesize several products as second-generation biofuels. Advances are presented on measures for reducing the presence of contaminants as tars, including the catalytic use of char for tar cracking; and in applications of the producer gas, including gas cleaning and direct coupling with a solid oxide fuel cell to maximize electricity production.

Keywords: gasification; bioenergy; emissions; tar; char; fuel cell.

1 INTRODUCTION

The current bioenergy uses and the state of the art in conversion technologies for producing bioheat, power and biofuels were recently reviewed in [1] (see also Figure 1). Although it is often overlooked in the public discussion, bioenergy is by far the most relevant renewable energy source available today. It is also the only renewable source that directly contributes to the three major energy uses: heat, electricity and transport.

Figure 1: Final energy consumption for different uses from modern bioenergy, other renewable energy sources (RES), non-renewable energy sources (Non-RES) and traditional biomass in 2017 in Europe (top) and worldwide (bottom) [1].

Despite the opportunities offered by bioenergy for all main energy uses, several barriers currently exist that block development. The main barriers for each main bioenergy use are:

- Bioheat: high emissions - mainly unburnt products (CO, volatile organic compounds and soot) for traditional biomass utilization; nitrogen oxides (NO_x) and inorganic particle matter (PM) emissions for modern automatic devices (see also Figure 2).
- Bioelectricity: limited electrical efficiency for processes based on combustion (see Figure 3), i.e. Organic Rankine cycles (< 2 MW_{el}) and steam cycles (> 2 MW_{el}).
- Biofuels: sustainability of first-generation biofuels and limited level of technical reliability for the production of second-generation biofuels from lignocellulosic biomass.

Figure 2: Typical PM emissions for wood combustion with different devices [1][2].

Biomass gasification is a key technology for energetic biomass utilization in the future that can overcome the current weakness, moving beyond conventional biomass combustion and first-generation biofuels. In this work, recent advances are presented on gasification-based technologies reached at TU Graz together with several partners to overcome these barriers. Results for selected examples will be now shown.

Figure 3: Electrical efficiencies and typical power ranges for bioelectricity production from biomass with different technologies [1].

2 MICROGASIFIERS FOR TRADITIONAL BIOMASS UTILIZATION

Around 2.7 billion people worldwide have no access to clean cooking equipment, which leads to major health problems due to high emissions of unburnt products. Globally, 3.8 million deaths were attributable to indoor air pollution in 2016, virtually all in low- and middle-income countries [3]. Micro-gasifiers based on the top lit updraft gasifier (TLUD) concept were identified as the technology with the highest potential for reducing harmful emissions from incomplete combustion in simple cookstoves. TLUD concepts with natural and forced draft were improved with simple methods that do not significantly increase the production costs, including a sufficiently large post-combustion chamber with insulation and ensuring a supply of an appropriate amount of primary air for a more stable fuel gasification [4][5] (see also Figure 4).

Figure 4: Scheme of improved TLUD cookstove with extended gas combustion chamber [4].

A significantly reduction in CO emissions was achieved with the improved designs [4][5], as shown in

Figure 5. Experiments and CFD simulation were employed to achieve this target. CO emissions are employed as an indicator for the burnout quality of the flue gas, and for the improved case with forced draft the obtained values are close to the range of automatic pellet furnaces for domestic heating, which are considered to be the benchmark for the best possible reduction of CO emissions.

Figure 5: CO emissions during the water boiling test for testing cookstoves (cold start) with basis (Awamu and FabStove) and improved TLUD variants, as well as comparison with emissions of other typical cookstoves (Gyapa charcoal stove and Envirofit G-3300 rocket stove - emissions from Jetter et al. [2]).

3 MODERN SMALL-SCALE BIOHEAT PRODUCTION WITH MINIMAL EMISSIONS

A novel small-scale multi-fuel biomass boiler concept was developed with the target to minimize emissions, including NO_x and PM, and to have a high feedstock flexibility. The concept is shown in Figure 6 and it was implemented in a 30 kW and a 200 kW boiler.

Figure 6: Scheme of the proposed concept for small-scale bioheat production with emissions reduction [6].

The bed conversion concept presented in [6] employs a low primary air ratio, resembling an updraft gasifier. Low PM emissions are obtained with this concept and flue gas recirculation can be included to achieve a high feedstock flexibility. An extended secondary zone under reduction conditions minimizes the NO_x emissions as presented in [7]. The tertiary zone ensures an efficient flue gas burnout to minimize the emissions of unburnt products as CO or soot. The obtained NO_x and PM emissions are presented in Figure 7 for the novel concept (in green) [7][8] in comparison to the state of the art for small-scale boilers. The obtained results indicate that very low PM emissions can be obtained for all fuels, as shown as well for a similar gasification-based concept [11], and that a reduction higher than 40% is obtained in NO_x emission in comparison to the state of the art for each tested fuel. Therefore, with the novel concept minimal emissions of PM and unburnt products and very low NO_x emissions can be achieved, as well as a high feedstock flexibility, which are significant improvements for small-scale bioheat production.

Figure 7: NO_x (top) and PM (bottom) emissions as a function of the N and K content of the fuel with the novel gasification-based concept (in green) compared with literature works (SotA-1= state-of-the-art Feldmeier et al. [9], SotA-2 = state-of-the-art Durand et al. [10], with NO_x extrapolation according to EN 303-5(2018) draft, UG = updraft gasifier with combustion chamber Obernberger et al. [11], Blend-2 = Díaz-Ramírez et al. [12], Blend-1 = Zeng et al. [13]). Results for 200 kW detailed in [8], NO_x for 30 kW in [7], PM for 30 kW not yet published. Data with primary recirculation for Miscanthus and secondary recirculation for wood chips.

4 IMPROVEMENTS IN GASIFICATION TECHNOLOGIES FOR THE PRODUCTION OF POWER AND FUELS

The status of the main gasification technologies for the production of bioelectricity and biofuels is summarized in Table I. The technical reliability and producer gas quality, specially of fluidized bed gasification, can be improved with several techniques,

including primary and secondary measures. Among primary measures, improvements can be obtained selecting an optimal bed material [14] or with new designs of fluidized beds, e.g. including a downdraft-based configuration of the gasification reactor with higher residence time at high temperatures in the dual fluidized bed design of TU Wien [15]. One promising option is to employ in the process char as a catalyst for tar conversion. Char is a by-product of gasification with a high activity for tar conversion and resistant to sulfur poisoning. However, char can be deactivated in short times by soot deposition [16]. Therefore, it is crucial to identify the required conditions to minimize or even suppress this possible char deactivation.

Table I: Overview of main biomass gasification technologies for power and biofuel production

	Fixed-bed with air	Fluidized-bed with steam
Scale	Small	Medium
Fuel flexibility	Low (wood chips / pellets)	Higher
Main application	Power	Biofuels (SNG, Fischer-Tropsch)
Status	Early commercialization (growing)	Limited commercialization / demonstration
Main limitation	Low fuel flexibility	Lower reliability / tars

Long-term tar conversion experiments with a char bed were conducted employing a real producer gas from fluidized bed gasification with steam of wood pellets. The results have shown that high tar conversion rates without major deactivation on long terms can be achieved with adequate reactor conditions, i.e. high steam contents and temperatures of 850°C or higher as shown in Figure 8 [17]. The integration of char as a catalyst for tar conversion in fluidized bed reactors is a promising alternative to increase the producer gas quality and therefore the attractiveness of these reactors [18].

Figure 8: Evolution of the tar conversion rate for tar cracking experiments conducted with a char bed at different temperatures and employing a real producer gas from a steam-blown fluidized-bed gasifier [17].

5 POWER PRODUCTION WITH FUEL CELLS

The current state of the art for power production based on solid biomass is shifting from biomass combustion to gasification coupled with gas engines, but according to thermodynamics much higher electrical efficiencies can be obtained with solid oxide fuel cells (SOFC) (see Figure 3)

Figure 9: Scheme of the coupling gasification – SOFC.

Several investigations have shown that it is feasible to employ the producer gas of biomass gasification in a fuel cell. It is recommendable to have a certain steam content in the producer gas [19] and even high steam contents (as from gasification with steam) can be employed [20]. Sulfur should be removed from the producer gas on the long-term, although short-term degradations due to H_2S can be regenerated [21]. However, the requirements for tar contents are not clear and can only be determined with real couplings.

A direct coupling of a fluidized bed gasifier with steam and a SOFC was conducted as shown in Figure 9. Gas cleaning consisted on PM removal and desulfurization. Regarding tars, heavy tars were partially removed through condensation in some cases. The results presented in Figure 10 show that employing a fluidized bed gasifier with a moderate tar content, operation with a Ni/YSZ cell (close to a broad commercialization) for several hours is possible without major degradation when heavy tars are removed, and degradation takes place fast only when heavy tars are present in the producer gas [22]. This shows the feasibility for these couplings when suitable producer gases and cells are employed.

Figure 10: Evolution of cell open circuit voltage (OCV) and power output (P) during long-term gasification-SOFC coupling with a Ni/YSZ cell at 850°C employing a real producer gas after desulfurization, with and without condensation of heavy tars, from a steam-blown fluidized-bed gasifier [22].

6 CONCLUSIONS

Developments in gasification-based processes can significantly contribute to increase the bioenergy use for bioheat, power and biofuels. Examples were presented for minimization of emissions produced in bioheat production based on gasification, improvements of

biomass gasification technologies to achieve a higher producer gas quality, or maximization of power production with direct coupling of biomass gasification with SOFCs. These advances tackle the current main barriers for increasing the use of bioenergy. The presented developments are close-to-market implementation or are obtained under investigations with long-term experiments for producer gas applications with a real producer gas. Therefore, they are a significant contribution for increasing the bioenergy use for bioheat, power and biofuels in the midterm.

7 REFERENCES

- [1] Anca-Couce, A., Hochenauer, C., & Scharler, R. (2021). Bioenergy technologies, uses, market and future trends with Austria as a case study. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 135, 110237.
- [2] Jetter, J., Zhao, Y., Smith, K. R., Khan, B., Yelverton, T., DeCarlo, P., & Hays, M. D. (2012). Pollutant emissions and energy efficiency under controlled conditions for household biomass cookstoves and implications for metrics useful in setting international test standards. *Environmental science & technology*, 46(19), 10827-10834.
- [3] WHO (2018). Burden of disease from household air pollution for 2016
- [4] Scharler, R., Archan, G., Rakos, C., von Berg, L., Lello, D., Hochenauer, C., & Anca-Couce, A. (2021). Emission minimization of a top-lit updraft gasifier cookstove based on experiments and detailed CFD analyses. *Energy Conversion and Management*, in review.
- [5] Archan, G., Blehrmühlhuber, M., Gregorc, J., García-Ramos, P., Muhumuza, N., Rakos, C., ... & Anca-Couce, A. (2019). Emissions reduction in a household biomass cook stove with a simple modification. In *European Biomass Conference and Exhibition Proceedings*, 684-687.
- [6] Archan, G., Anca-Couce, A., Gregorc, J., Buchmayr, M., Hochenauer, C., Gruber, J., & Scharler, R. (2020). Detailed experimental investigation of the spatially distributed gas release and bed temperatures in fixed-bed biomass combustion with low oxygen concentration. *Biomass and Bioenergy*, 141, 105725.
- [7] Archan, G., Scharler, R., Pölzer, L., Buchmayr, M., Sommersacher, P., Hochenauer, C., Gruber, J., & Anca-Couce, A. (2021). Detailed NO_x precursor measurements within the reduction zone of a novel small-scale fuel flexible biomass combustion technology. *Fuel*, in review.
- [8] Archan, G., Anca-Couce, A., Buchmayr, M., Hochenauer, C., Gruber, J., & Scharler, R. (2021).

- Experimental evaluation of primary measures for NO_x and dust emission reduction in a novel 200 kW multi-fuel biomass boiler. *Renewable energy*, 170, 1186-1196.
- [9] Feldmeier, S., Wopienka, E., Schwarz, M., Schön, C., & Pfeifer, C. (2019). Applicability of Fuel Indexes for Small-Scale Biomass Combustion Technologies, Part 2: TSP and NO_x Emissions. *Energy and Fuels*, 33, 11724–30.
- [10] Durand, A., Götz, T., Thema, J., Dittus, F., & Hübschmann, M. (2014). EU-UltraLowDust Project. D7.6: Final report. Information Material and Policy Recommendations. Wuppertal.
- [11] Obernberger, I., Thek, G., Brunner, T., Nowak, P., Mandl, C., Kerschbaum, M., et al. (2018). Next generation fuel flexible residential biomass heating based on an extreme air staging technology with ultra-low emissions. *Eur Biomass Conf Exhib Proc*, 2018, 7–15.
- [12] Díaz-Ramírez, M., Sebastián, F., Royo, J., & Rezeau, A. (2014). Influencing factors on NO_x emission level during grate conversion of three pelletized energy crops. *Applied energy*, 115, 360-373.
- [13] Zeng, T., Weller, N., Pollex, A., & Lenz, V. (2016). Blended biomass pellets as fuel for small scale combustion appliances: Influence on gaseous and total particulate matter emissions and applicability of fuel indices. *Fuel*, 184, 689-700.
- [14] Soria-Verdugo, A., Von Berg, L., Serrano, D., Hochenauer, C., Scharler, R., & Anca-Couce, A. (2019). Effect of bed material density on the performance of steam gasification of biomass in bubbling fluidized beds. *Fuel*, 257, 116118.
- [15] Benedikt, F., Schmid, J. C., Fuchs, J., Mauerhofer, A. M., Müller, S., & Hofbauer, H. (2018). Fuel flexible gasification with an advanced 100 kW dual fluidized bed steam gasification pilot plant. *Energy*, 164, 329-343.
- [16] Ravenni, G., Sárossy, Z., Ahrenfeldt, J., & Henriksen, U. B. (2018). Activity of chars and activated carbons for removal and decomposition of tar model compounds—a review. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 94, 1044-1056.
- [17] Fuentes-Cano, D., Von Berg, L., Diéguez-Alonso, A., Scharler, R., Gómez-Barea, A., & Anca-Couce, A. (2020). Tar conversion of biomass syngas in a downstream char bed. *Fuel processing technology*, 199, 106271.
- [18] Gómez-Barea, A., Leckner, B., Perales, A. V., Nilsson, S., & Cano, D. F. (2013). Improving the performance of fluidized bed biomass/waste gasifiers for distributed electricity: a new three-stage gasification system. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 50(2), 1453-1462.
- [19] Subotić, V., Baldinelli, A., Barelli, L., Scharler, R., Pongratz, G., Hochenauer, C., & Anca-Couce, A. (2019). Applicability of the SOFC technology for coupling with biomass-gasifier systems: Short-and long-term experimental study on SOFC performance and degradation behaviour. *Applied Energy*, 256, 113904.
- [20] Pongratz, G., Subotić, V., Schroettner, H., Stoeckl, B., Hochenauer, C., Anca-Couce, A., & Scharler, R. (2021). Investigation of solid oxide fuel cell operation with synthetic biomass gasification product gases as a basis for enhancing its performance. *Biomass Conversion and Biorefinery*, 11(1), 121-139.
- [21] Pongratz, G., Subotić, V., Schröttner, H., Hochenauer, C., Skrzypkiewicz, M., Kupecki, J., Anca-Couce, A., & Scharler, R. (2021). Analysis of H₂S-related short-term degradation and regeneration of anode-and electrolyte supported solid oxide fuel cells fueled with biomass steam gasifier product gas. *Energy*, 218, 119556.
- [22] Pongratz, G., Subotic, V., von Berg, L., Schroettner, H., Hochenauer, C., Martini, S., ... & Anca-Couce, A. (2021). Real coupling of solid oxide fuel cells with a biomass steam gasifier: Operating boundaries considering performance, tar and carbon deposition analyses. *Journal of Power Sources*, in review.

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